

Economic Analysis on Health Insurance Schemes Among Professional Drivers in Erode District of Tamilnadu

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Abstract

By the observation of source of treatment as health care services, sample respondents mostly attract with performance of private hospitals. On the other hand highly expense are there, avail the treatment at free of cost in government hospitals. so study reveals that the basic need to analyze about contribution of health insurance schemes among the sample respondents in selected areas due to face the risk of high expenses on health when illness. Health insurance to meet the cost of hospitalization for major illness will ensure that health care costs do not become a major burden or cause of indebtedness among several health insurance schemes have been introduced. There are individual, family and group insurance for specific diseases. Awareness about need to cover major healthcare expenses increased exposure through media, most importantly the internet, lead to increase in demand for better medical facilities. It found that out of 600, most of the drivers had aware about the health insurance and rest of them did not aware. By this result among 600, 288 drivers were enrolled in health insurance schemes and 312 drivers not enrolled.

Keywords: Health care, Health Insurance, medical costs.

Health as define, composed by specialists in preventive medicine, specifies some tangible components of health "a state characterized by anatomical, physiological, and psychological integrity; ability to perform personally valued family, work, and community roles; ability to deal with physical, biological, psychological, and social stress; a feeling of well-being; and freedom from the risk of disease and untimely death" (Stokes et al. 1982)¹. Health insurance is a type of insurance where by the insurer pays the medical costs of the insured become sick due to covered causes, or due to accidents. Market based health care systems such as that in India rely on private medical insurance it is also called accident and sickness insurance, medical insurance. In general, any insurance program covering medical expenses /or income lost owing to illness or accidental injure such insurance may cover some or all of the expense of hospitalization, surgery, physician's fees,

drugs and medicines, laboratory tests, X-rays and other diagnostic procedures, radiation therapy, maternity and nursing care, eyeglasses, crutches, prostheses and etc.

Health Expenditure For Health Insurance

Over 300 million people, or more than 25 percent of India's population, gained access to some form of health insurance by 2010, up from 55 million in 2003-04. The report projects that more than 630 million persons, or about half of the country's population, can be covered with health insurance by 2015. About 20 per cent of the total health expenditure was financed by the Central Government, State Government and local bodies while external flows accounted for 2 per cent of the total health expenditure. The challenge improve efficiency in the use allocation of funds to the health sector both at the Central and State level².

Review of Literature

John Nyman (2001)³ analyzed in theory of the demand for health insurance presented that suggested the moral hazard was primarily an income transfer effect. In an estimation based on parameters from the literature, the value of moral hazard consumption is found to be three times greater than its costs, suggested that income transferred effects dominate price effects and that moral hazard was welfare-increased.

Machnes (2006)⁴ explored the study about the demand for private health care and supplemental health insurance in Israel. He describes the 11,090 households in the surveyed population, revealing that 15 per cent spent money on private health care and 12 per cent had purchased commercial supplemental health insurance. The logit and the Probit regressions describe the probability of incurring expenditure, while the Tobit regression described the sum of money spent for private health care, found that the self-employed demand more private health services and health insurance than wage-earners.

Santerre (2006)⁵ developed a model to demand for health insurance incorporated assessed value as being derived from the demand for good health. Based on multiple regression analysis, he used national data (1960-2002) explained changes in the marginal access value of private health insurance over time at the national level in the United States it was slowed the growth of the marginal access value of private health insurance.

David Cutler (2003)⁶ in his paper "Employee Costs and the Decline in Health Insurance Coverage", described the problems—high costs, inefficient production, and lack of security and the demand for healthcare. Poor people when they need healthcare they neither go to private hospital nor the public hospitals, because of high costs in private hospitals and in efficient production and lack of security in public hospitals. When these problems exist the demand for healthcare varies according to the situation.

Okunade et al. (2002)⁷ indicated that the real aggregate health care expenditure per capita does respond to Research and Development expenditure continues to rise at historical rates and real income rises, health insurance is likely to be more expensive or change characteristics e.g. higher deductibles, more supply-side rationing and had equity ramifications.

Ray et al. (2002)⁸ stated information on healthcare expenditure and health services of the family or household in India. They resulted the private health sector was utilized in 59.4 per cent of Utilization of the private sector was directly associated with a higher socioeconomic status. The total expenditure on non-hospitalized cases, 83.6 per cent was (Rs 131 mean per capita and 15 median) incurred in the private sector. They suggested need for systems such as health insurance to protect the poor from high medical costs.

Pauly and Levin (1990)⁹ observed the demand for long-term health insurance may be mitigated by the presence of a social insurance program in India. They mentioned the greater persistence and variation in health expenses would reduce the demand for private health insurance relative on medic aid in the event of a health downturn. They expected risk and level of health spending was likely estimated coefficients implied and one increase in, out of pocket medical spending was associate with and future out-of-pocket spending.

Methodology

The specific objectives have been set for the study to explain about the socio-economic status of the selected drivers and to analyze the theory of demand for health care services and health insurance schemes for drivers. The study analyzed about performances of the health insurance schemes among professional drivers of the Erode district. Primary data and secondary data were collected in Blocks were namely Erode, Gobichettipalayam, Bhavani, Perundurai and Sathyamangalam, stratified into one stratum as drivers. In each blocks, drivers were selected based on the nature of heavy vehicle i.e. 12 categories. In each of the selected blocks, 120 drivers each 10 per stratum was selected from each of the categories of Drivers like Lorry, Truck, Tempo, bus, Tourist bus, Auto, Mini-Dore, Tractor, Omni, car and other types of heavy vehicles.

Respondent's Contribution of Health Insurance Schemes

Policies differ in what they cover, the size of the deductible and or co-payment, limits of coverage and the options for treatment available to the policyholder. The health insurance is a vital method of financing the spiraling costs of medical care. The high cost of hospital services coupled with the unpredictability of health needs and the inadequacy of personal savings is the primary reason for the growing importance of insurance as a means of financing health services. In spite of the growing importance of health insurance schemes the number of people covered by health insurance is very less in India. By this study It found that out of 600, most of the drivers (87.67 per cent) had aware about the health insurance and rest of them (12.33 per cent) did not aware. This result among 600, 288 drivers (48 per cent) enrolled in health insurance schemes and 312 drivers (52 per cent) not enrolled. Out of 600 drivers, 312 were not subscribing any kind of health insurance schemes. 37.2 per cent respondents felt that the premium amount was high, 19 per cent considered it is not necessary because they were healthy, 5.4 per cent were not interested, most of them 29.5 per cent could not afford it and 9 per cent were wealthy and did not want any assistance.

Types of Health Insurance Schemes of Sample Respondents

In India, various organizations avail health insurance schemes, in the study area only (6.6 per cent) 19 respondents had government's health insurance that implies free of cost and cut the medical expenses by people out of pocket and but most of them 288 drivers (93.4 per cent) were joined in the private health insurance. Based on private health insurance (269 drivers), 77 respondents (26.7 per cent) enrolled in ICICI Star Health Insurance and 56 respondents (19.4 per cent) were joined in Bajaj Health Insurance. Meantime 27 respondents (9.4 per cent) took Bharti Health Insurance and 18 respondents (6.3 per cent) were enrolled in Mahindra Health Insurance. Only 26 respondents (9 per cent) took HDFC Health Insurance. Finally most of them (29.2 per cent) were enrolled in Star Health Insurance. Out of 307 drivers, only 5 respondents (1.6 per cent) were benefited by government health insurance card and 34 respondents (11.1 per cent) were benefitted by private health insurance schemes. But most of them, 87.3 per cent were not benefitted yet by both organizations. But then again they were continued to pay the premium amount for health insurance schemes.

5.17 Driver’s opinion’s on Motivation, Source of Payment and Premium Amount

Motivation is very crucial for joining to the health insurance otherwise no one share benefit of health insurance schemes and escape from more health expenditure burden. After the joined premium will pay by respondents during time period and what are the sources involved in payment and how much amount of money are spend to health insurance as premium. Suppose premium amount will be higher than respondent’s monthly income they should prefer the reason not subscribe the health insurance schemes. Most of them 34 per cent of them (98 respondents) were joined as own. Meanwhile 9.7 per cent (28 respondents) were motivated by television and friends respectively. 60 respondents nearby 21 per cent were motivated by newspaper. Only 8 per cent of them 23 respondents were motivated by of the family members for the health insurance. Nearly 6 per cent (17 respondents) were motivated by Insurance agents for the health insurance scheme. Finally, 11.8 per cent (34 respondents) were motivated by beneficiaries of Insurance. Basis of Source of payment for health insurance, out of 288, 282 sample respondents (98 per cent) were paid premium by own revenue and rest of them 2.1 per cent were paid by their company or organizations. In the study area, typically most of the respondents were paying below Rs.5000 and followed by they were paying Rs.1001 to 5000 and but few respondents were paid above Rs. 10000 as annual health insurance premium. Among the respondents most of them (73 per cent) were fully satisfied and 21.2 per cent were partially satisfied and followed by 3.8 per cent of them was not satisfied by health services provided by health insurance schemes. Finally 2.1 per cent of the respondents have given no response for related question.

Driver’s Demand for Health Insurance

It was revealed that corrupted persons are working as agents in health insurance schemes so that they had problems so it has first rank. Next to this, expectation of respondents there is Inadequate of facilities on payment in schemes thus they reported as second rank. Drivers claimed Low coverage in schemes therefore that had third rank and medical and paramedical staff gives poor quality of services based on schemes payment so that had fourth rank. High cost on payments for premium on the way they claimed it was fifth rank as problem. Offices are far away from respondent’s household basis of large distances and inconvenient locations to travel there so they mentioned as sixth rank. If respondents unsatisfied the facilities or services of health insurance schemes they cannot withdrawal the money it had seventh rank as problem faced by sample respondents.

Table 5.22 Problems Faced by Respondents for Health Insurance Premium

Factors	Rank	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Total Value	Mean Value	Rank
	S.V	78	65	57	50	42	34	21			
Low coverage	F	22	86	9	66	26	58	21	288	50.78	III
	Fx	1716	5590	513	3300	1092	1972	441	14624		
Poor quality of services	F	46	43	39	24	19	73	44	288	48.65	IV
	Fx	3588	2795	2223	1200	798	2482	924	14010		
High cost	F	43	23	61	31	20	41	69	288	47.08	V
	Fx	3354	1495	3477	1550	840	1394	1449	13559		
Inadequate facilities	F	72	25	24	48	52	46	21	288	52.77	II
	Fx	5616	1625	1368	2400	2184	1564	441	15198		
Withdrawing problems	F	23	40	49	10	67	56	43	288	46.21	VII
	Fx	1794	2600	2793	500	2814	1904	903	13308		

Long distance and inconvenient locations	F	39	26	26	61	60	6	70	288	46.73	VI
	Fx	3042	1690	1482	3050	2520	204	1470	13458		
Corruption	F	43	45	80	48	44	8	20	288	54.79	I
	Fx	3354	2925	4560	2400	1848	272	420	15779		
Total		288	288	288	288	288	288	288			

Source: Computed

Table 5.23 Factors Responsible for Determine the Health Insurance Schemes

Factors	Rank	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Total Score	Mean Value	Rank
	S V	78	65	57	50	42	34	21			
Amount of cost coverage	F	21	87	101	39	17	16	7	288	56.96	I
	Fx	1638	5655	5757	1950	714	544	147	16405		
Treatment coverage	F	47	43	35	57	43	29	34	288	51.43	III
	Fx	3666	2795	1995	2850	1806	986	714	14812		
Medicines	F	69	13	28	33	48	37	60	288	48.64	IV
	Fx	5382	845	1596	1650	2016	1258	1260	14007		
Diagnostic Services	F	92	32	14	35	32	41	42	288	53.56	II
	Fx	7176	2080	798	1750	1344	1394	882	15424		
Hospital Charges	F	25	43	21	31	42	80	46	288	44.94	VI
	Fx	1950	2795	1197	1550	1764	2720	966	12942		
Specialist Consultation	F	12	42	31	31	67	46	59	288	43.75	VII
	Fx	2730	1767	1550	2814	1564	1239	12600	24264		
Consultation Coverage	F	22	28	58	62	39	39	40	288	47.73	V
	Fx	1716	1820	3306	3100	1638	1326	840	13746		
Total		288	288	288	288	288	288	288			

Source: Computed

The above table explained results of Hendry Garrett ranking technique that indicated factors determine to responsible for the success of health insurance schemes among respondents. In the total 288 respondents preferred the amount of cost coverage should be less comfortable for their income so that factor influenced as first rank so low income and middle income respondents were predicted the expenses of medical and they chose suitable cost coverage due to their earning capacity. In case respondents had illness and injuries they must need good medical services by diagnostic services so they preferred it as second rank. Treatment for illness must incorporate with health insurance schemes thus it was chosen fourth rank. After that, medicines plays important role in cure of diseases and injuries so they hope that will be under the health insurance schemes it has fourth rank. Meanwhile consultation coverage factor was chosen as fifth rank, so they preferred good consultation from medical professional when illness on basis of health insurance remuneration process. Hospital charges is one of the burden it imposes cash as out of expenditure for respondents so they faith to include that in insurance schemes as sixth rank. Finally, respondents expect the

specialist consultation for definite diseases will be include in schemes thus it was preferred as seventh rank by them.

Determinants of Health Insurance Schemes

The mentioned variables are to analyze the simple linear regression to find out the factors determining to increasing demand for health insurance with reference determinants of health insurance schemes. This descriptive statistics analysis elaborates the trends of variables to slot in with variables for health insurance schemes among respondents.

Descriptive Statistics for Health Insurance Schemes

Descriptive Statistics			
Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Health Insurance schemes	1.9340	0.24867	288
Age in years	1.4271	0.66382	288
nature of family	1.0868	0.28204	288
Religion	1.1181	0.44167	288
Social Status	2.4444	0.69621	288
Nativity	1.6875	0.93308	288
Education	3.4271	0.94531	288
Monthly Income of Respondents	3.0470	0.64121	288

Source: Computed

Beneficiaries of health insurance schemes in the study, they were demanded the schemes stimulate the strength of their life after the treatment and about the condition of activities by government and private institution performance comparatively worse while cost of treatment occurred to occupy the contribution of health insurance schemes among sample respondents. On the specified results of descriptive statistics which constitutes the mean value of their educational level and monthly income were high than other variables. Therefore it was found that those contribution was delivered when the facilities received by health insurance schemes but it simulates task thriving the facts existed mentioned above variables. In the middle of point, mean value of social status was identified significantly corporates after education and income condition of respondents whereas before the others variables with proof of uniqueness were done with origin of the circumstance of health insurance schemes.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.151a	.673	.439	.25066

a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Sample Respondents, Social Status, nature of family, Education, Age in years, Nature of birth place, Religion.

The table explains the model fit of our study which explains the R = 67.3 per cent and Adjusted R²=44. In this inference study get optimum level of model fit because used to analyze binary variables also as explanatory variables so automatically that may get less model fit.

Table 5.26 Results of ANOVAb

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	0.390	7	.056	.898	.509a
	Residual	17.357	280	.062		
	Total	17.747	287			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Sample Respondents, Religion, nature of family, Social Status, Education, Age in years, Nature of birth place.

b. Dependent Variable: Health Insurance schemes. The ANOVA table explains that explanatory variables are significantly influenced on the demand for health insurance and willingness to pay capacity. It was used N= 288 (subjects) and level of significant is at 5 % level. The following regression coefficient table explains the factors determining demand for health insurance.

Table Co-efficients a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.033	.131	-	15.518	.000
	Age in years	.371	.023	-.033	-.547	.585
	nature of family	.408	.054	.054	.892	.373
	Religion	-.319	.034	-.069	-1.135	.257
	Social Status	.209	.022	.025	.420	.675
	Nature of birth place	.364	.017	-.136	-2.168	.031
	Educational	.695	.016	-.035	-.590	.556
	Monthly Income	-.741	.023	-.017	-.279	.781

a. Dependent Variable: Health Insurance schemes

Source: Computed

$$\text{Formula} = \text{Ln}Y = \alpha + \beta_1(x_1) + \beta_2(x_2) + \beta_3(x_3) + \beta_4(x_4) + \beta_5(x_5) + \beta_6(x_6) + (\text{Ln}x_7) + \mu$$

$\text{Ln}Y$ = Health Insurance schemes.
 x_1 = Sex of the Sample respondent
 x_2 = Religion
 x_3 = Social Background
 x_4 = Type of family
 x_5 = Age
 x_6 = Nature of the Birth Place
 x_7 = Log income

Ln (Health Insurance Schemes) =	2.033(constant) + .695 (Education) + -.319 (Religion) + .046 (Social Background + .209 (Type of Family) + .371 (Age) + .364 (Nativity) -.741 (Ln Monthly Income) + μ
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Health Insurance schemes = 2.033 + .371+ .408 -.319+.209+.364+.695-.741

In the table researcher used to analyze the factors behind for the demand for health insurance determine. Study got three important elements to determine and influence to have high level of determine to pay for health insurance. They are type of family, age and income of the family all the significant explanatory variables are statistically significant at 5 % level. Log function has been used to neutralize skewness of the data explained in econometrics models as above. According to results, hypothesized the range of the demand on health insurance has solution based on the direction of variation e.g., are the poor/ rich more sensitive to the price, but the results of study, found that no variation or the opposite effect e.g., the rich are more price sensitive to the price than the poor is expected. From the hypothetical questions, here self-insured health plans were benefited and accepted the more facilities on demand basis at affordable prices to cut medical expenses.

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